

CUSTOM MACHINE LEARNING IN SENSOR-DRIVEN HOTELS

An experimental take on practical use of machine learning in the hotel industry, using Sundvolden Hotel as a case, specifically focusing on: sensor-based facilitation, merging conference planning with IoT through machine learning and visualizing airflow via simulation, in an attempt to gain deeper insight in personalized/demand based indoor occupancy.

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Abstract

This report explores the integration of machine learning (ML) in the hotel industry, using Sundvolden Hotel as a case study to investigate operational potential of ML in sensor driven environments. The study introduces an experimental framework called Trained Machine Facilitation (TMF), which applies Industry 4.0 technologies to optimize operations and management, with an example within ventilation.

Based on data from 19 [Airthings](#) sensors (1-year time span) and the hotel's own conference schedule (3-year time span), three specific models were applied: *Heimdall* for outlier/anomaly detection, *Munin* for predicting sensor values based on expected attendee numbers from the conference schedule, and *Hugin* for forecasting attendee numbers from sensor data.

The results demonstrate the transformative power of ML as a tool to enhance operational efficiency through real-time and historical data insights. Heimdall excelled in identifying anomalies/outliers and achieved an F1-score of 0.97 (97%), underscoring its reliability as a gatekeeper for sensor data. Munin, after thorough data cleaning and optimization, achieved a high predictive accuracy with an R-squared of 0.904 (90.4%). However, Hugin faced challenges in forecasting attendee numbers, underscoring the complexities of sensor-driven predictions and data accessibility.

Among the algorithms tested, the Random Forest algorithm emerged as the most robust, excelling in both prediction and processing efficiency. Additionally, the report emphasizes the critical role of data harmonization, prompt engineering and preprocessing in order to achieve reliable and high-quality predictive outcomes in dynamic sensor rich environments.

Finally, the report concludes by evaluating and discussing the broader implications of integrating machine learning into building management systems, emphasizing the importance of choosing appropriate models for specific data-circumstances.

Foreword

This study has been conducted in collaboration with the Norwegian energy-efficiency and facilitation company Energy Control and the renowned conference hotel, Sundvolden Hotel, located approximately 40 minutes outside Oslo. The project constitutes the final component of the Applied Machine Learning program at Noroff University College and corresponds to 10 ECTS. This report was reviewed by program manager Bertram Haskins, 24.10.2024.

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1. Introduction

The hospitality industry is undergoing a significant transformation driven by advancements in technology, especially in the field of machine learning (ML) and artificial intelligence (AI). These technologies offer innovative solutions to enhance guest and staff experience and improving operational efficiency. This project focuses on leveraging sensor-driven data and conference schedule data to explore how different ML-algorithms performs based on their specific task.

ML and AI have the potential to revolutionize hotel operations from the moment a guest considers booking a room, to their post stay experience. Fresh articles on this topic reveal how AI is already transforming various aspects of the hospitality industry including operations, sales, guest journey, revenue management, marketing, and human resources. Hollander.J (2024)

By utilizing sensor-based facilitation, hotels can gather real-time data on environmental factors, in this case temperature, co2-level and humidity, which are the 3 most crucial parameters for optimal indoor comfort.

Moreover, integrating [Internet of Things\(IoT\)](#) devices with conference management systems can streamline the planning and execution of events. Given that hardware-technology like sensors has become increasingly better, IoT-enabled sensors and ML algorithms have the potential to monitor room occupancy, predict energy usage, adjust environmental controls in real life, thereby improving efficiency and reducing operational costs.

The findings are not just theoretical but also practical implementations that illustrate the transformative power of AI and ML in creating a responsive and dynamic hotel environment, where modern tech-based insight like tailormade ML models for conference planning and facilitation are easily available. This report will guide you to see how technology could be shaping the future of building facilitation and indoor climate, providing a responsive and dynamic environment tailored to the individual occupant's need.

2. Background

2.1 Industry 4.0 and 5.0 in construction and facilitation

The construction and facilitation sector are currently undergoing a significant transformation, driven by the converge of traditional building practises with modern technology. This transition, often referred to as the shift from [Industry 4.0](#) to [Industry 5.0](#), emphasizes not only the automation and data exchange introduced in Industry 4.0, but also the integration of human centric approaches, prompt engineering and sustainable development.

Industry 4.0 is entered on the idea of merging information, technology, and people to create smart, interconnected environments within factories and infrastructure through cyber-physical systems. Although the shift towards this vision is still underway, the concept of Industry 5.0 has already begun to take shape. Industry 5.0 emphasizes the reintegration of human workers into the production process, promoting collaboration between humans and robots to create a more synergistic and cooperative working environment (Marinelli, 2023)

Industry 4.0 brought advancements such as [IoT \(internet of things\)](#), [digital twins](#), big data analytics, 3rd generation AI, and cloud computing, which enables smarter and more efficient building processes. As the modern world move towards Industry 5.0 there is a growing emphasis on leveraging machine learning and artificial intelligence with respect to computer-human interaction, to create more responsive and adaptive systems within the construction industry. These technologies facilitate real-time monitoring, predictive maintenance-operations and automated decision making. This has an indescribable potential to enhance daily productivity, reduce costs and improve safety by having detailed control opportunities. All these recent developments create a world-wide demand for higher level of data-logging, data-availability, and data-harmonization, especially in the construction sector.

2.2 Sundvolden Hotel and Energy Control

Sundvolden Hotel, located 35 minutes north of Oslo, has since 2019 embraced hypermodern technology to enhance guest comfort, operational efficiency, and facilitation control. Partnering with [Energy Control](#), the hotel has integrated a state-of-the-art sensor system throughout the whole hotel, step by step. Ultimately achieving a level of detailed insight and control, by using cloud-based sensor systems and a dashboard for remote insight and control that has proved to be exceptionally helpful and effective in daily operations and facilitation.

There are three main types of sensors: [Airthings](#), which measures indoor parameters, the most important being: Co2, temperature and humidity. The second type of sensors is Disruptive Technologies, which are mini sensors placed on components of [HVACR](#)-systems to

provide cloud-based wireless operational insight. The last sensor type being energy-measurement sensors. This combined data is then used to optimize the hotel's HVACR and facilitation system by ensuring a consistently comfortable indoor environment for guests as well as providing a facilitation foundation that enhances detailed insight and zone control. The sensor system was implemented in different stages, gradually improving the overall system. This has led to a reduction in energy consumption by approximately 20-25% when looking at the hotel's 3 most important energy sources (pellets, electricity, and gas), comparing the result for 2018 (before the cloud-based sensor system) to 2022 (after the sensor system was implemented), according to the hotel's own records.

Energy Control has been instrumental in this technological advancement, they provided the design and installation of the sensor-network, as well as a cloud-based platform that analyses and display the collected data, simplifying facilitation insight. Using set point-based algorithms and responding to real time sensor values, the system automatically adjusts HVACR settings to the needed state. The collaboration between Sundvolden Hotel and Energy Control exemplifies the benefits of Industry 4.0 technologies in the hospitality industry, showcasing how data-driven insights can lead to improved operational efficiency and enhanced guest experience.

2.3 Tommy Hagenes- Bridging the gap between property and technology.

In an interview with Tomy Hagenes, the managing director of Energy Control, crucial insights emerge regarding the importance of data harmonization, cloud-based solutions, and data availability for operational efficiency.

Tommy highlights the initial challenges for the faced by the industry, noting that only about 15% of smaller buildings worldwide are managed effectively, which spurred the creation of Energy Control. The company aimed to make older, smaller buildings smarter by leveraging new, wireless battery-powered technology. This innovative approach has since expanding to managing much larger buildings due to customer satisfaction and demand, demonstrating the scalability and adaptability of their solutions.

A significant part of the interview revolved around the transformation brought by digitalization through sensor systems, as Hagenes states: - *"Should work without you noticing it"*, ensuring seamless integration and minimal disruption. He points out that the current industry standard does not utilize sensors to their full potential for building management, indicating the gap that Energy Control aims to fill.

Tommy also elaborates in the practical advantages of using open [API's](#) and the cloud to enhance operational efficiency through a tailor-made solution. By integrating modern sensors with open API's, Energy Control can access vast amounts of external data sources, like

electricity prices from Nordpool and historical energy data going back five years. This integration allows for real-time, data-driven decision-making, which is crucial for understanding energy consumption patterns and optimizing operations effectively.

Furthermore, the capability to quickly implement these technologies in fully operational buildings has been instrumental. Transitioning from traditional month-long projects to an agile project sprint, that gets the work done in a couple of days. This rapid deployment not only underscores the practicality of Energy Control's approach, but also its economic viability, supporting the industrial claims that data harmonization and accessible cloud-based solutions are essential in revolutionizing building automation.

2.3 Trained Machine Facilitation (TMF)

This report proposes a test-concept called Trained Machine Facilitation (TMF). This is a theoretical facilitation technique, designed to optimize daily operations and overall efficiency in the facilitation industry of the world.

The definition of TMF would be: Using machine learning, AI or other computing technology to enhance insight/simplify processes etc. within a building's 4 cornerstones: Technical, Economic, Judicial or Social insight.

The TMF concept represents a holistic approach to optimizing building operations. By integrating technologies per the definition of TMF. It aims to create intelligent self-adapting systems that can continuously improve efficiency, indoor comfort, data insight, energy source handling etc. Which aligns with the principles of Industry 5.0 by emphasizing the integration of human-centric approaches and sustainable development alongside automation and data exchange. (Cheng, et al, 2021)

2.4 TMF-example: Ventilation

TMF within ventilation operates based on three core principles: demand-controlled ventilation through zone-based management, simulation (in this case airflow), and historic and real-time group comfort levels. Through this, the operator and or machine, can gain and display detailed insight when hosting a large number of occupants within a confined area.

TMF should be designed to give insights to maintain optimal comfort levels for all occupants. It considers the collective comfort preferences based on historical data of groups within each zone, adjusting factors such as temperature, humidity and airflow/air exchange rate to create a comfortable environment tailored to the occupants needs.

The reason for this experimental view on ventilation and facilitation bases itself on the variability of energy sources, indoor comfort circumstances and cost reduction parameters like electricity market, where buildings such as hotels could benefit from automated and machine-interactive data-insight. (Wu et al., 2022)

TMF is essentially not a specific program, but more of a technique where both professionals and non-professionals can apply the concepts of TMF to improve their current facilitation and ensure that the building meets TMF requirements, which includes a cost-effect perspective. For example, very old buildings will have difficulties being fully integrated due to the electrical and building-technical requirements that is needed for full sensor integration and is therefore limited in using TMF due to the missing technical features of the existing facilitation system.

However, by installing a system of sensors like [Airthings](#), the history you get from the sensor is more than enough (as a first step) to identify potential processes, components, areas etc that could need improvement. For example, Airthings' sensortype that includes air pressure in its measurements, could be very effective in guiding towards identifying air leakage, which is one of many key components to heat loss when it comes to a buildings' energy efficiency. (Hun et al., 2014)

2.4.1 Demand controlled ventilation

Demand controlled ventilation aka DCV, adjusts the airflow in real time according to the registered number of occupants and their activity levels. Required quality for ventilation systems would include having more recent HVACR-systems with techniques like VAV(variable air volume), VRV(variable refrigerant volume) and Industry 4.0 technology such as cloud-based monitoring, automated control, remote control and [digital twins](#). The improvements DCV offers, are made possible by technology developments such as upgraded sensor hardware and upgraded system components (f.ex Unipi, which is a Raspberry Pi based control device that automates HVACR control). By constantly responding to the actual needs of a space, the DCV system ensures that ventilation is not only provided where and when it is necessary, but also reducing energy consumption and operational costs due to real-time action and reaction.

The implementation of demand-controlled ventilation (DCV) within TMF requires the integration of various industry 4.0 technologies. This includes the use of advanced sensors networks to monitor occupancy and activity levels, as well as cloud-based analytics and automated control systems to adjust ventilation rates in real time. By leveraging these technologies like Energy Control has done at Sundvolden Hotel, DCV can achieve significant energy savings while maintaining optimal indoor air quality (IAQ), contributing to the overall goals of TMF and industry 5.0. According to Cheng et al.(2021), DCV systems will reduce

energy consumption while maintaining or improving indoor air quality by responding to the actual occupancy need in real time.

2.4.2 Zone-based management

Zone based management subdivides buildings into specific zones, to narrow down the level of detail for commercial buildings or buildings with varying activity levels. This technique offers independent control of the airflow to each zone, ensuring that areas with higher registered occupancy or activity receive more ventilation, while unoccupied or less active areas receive less. This targeted approach enhances overall efficiency and indoor comfort.

Zone based management is a key component of the TMF approach in HVACR systems, enabling a targeted control and optimization of building systems at a granular level. By subdividing into zones, TMF can ensure that resources are allocated efficiently based on actual occupancy and activity levels within each zone. This level of precision and adaptability aligns with the goals of Industry 5.0. Goyal et al. (2013) highlight that zone-level control can significantly reduce HVACR energy consumption by tailoring the environmental conditions to the need of each zone. For Sundvolden Hotel, the zone-usage is extremely variable, with multiple rooms and buildings being simultaneously used for varying activity types, thus emphasising the need for zone-based management.

2.4.3 Airflow simulation

By simulating conference events, the owner, facilitator, staff, guests etc, gets the opportunity to view an accurate depiction of the conference hall's air circumstances. Either if its to simulate airflow in order to know how to most effectively place the chairs related to conference setup, or the facilitators keen insight in how different [ACH](#) affects indoor conference climate and airflow can be visualized.

According to Zhai et al.(2002), coupling energy simulation with computational fluid dynamics (CFD) can provide detailed insight into airflow patterns and energy consumption, which can be crucial for optimizing ventilation strategies in large spaces like conference halls. This can lead to more efficient HVACR operations and improved occupant comfort.

Figure 1: A sequential visual representation of airflow in conference hall 1 (building 2017) at Sundvolden Hotel. Simulation was done via Simscale CFD (computational fluid dynamics).

This is a depiction of airflow during a conference held on 16 April 2024 for “Hole Kommune”. The event hosted 100 attendees, arranged at group tables with 8 individuals per table. Additional details about this conference are available in figure 3, which displays the original conference pdf.

The potential for integrating simulations in daily facilitation is huge considering modern tech quality/accessibility. If every system component or room can be simulated under different circumstances, and combined into ML adapted datasets, it provides an information basis that is creating a profound foundation for efficient control and room monitoring. However, the cost-effectiveness and processing power required for such implementations are significant considerations. Both simulations and ML models demand substantial computational resources, highlighting the need for a balanced approach that leverages advanced technology with budget and power constraints.

3. Problem statement

How can applied machine learning, AI and simulations enhance facilitation insight within the hotel sector and facilitation industry, given the recent advancements in sensor technology and cloud computing where the focus lies on data availability.

4. Project objectives

The main objective for this project is to demonstrate a fraction of [TMF](#) by creating 3 experimental ML-models that use sensor data and conference schedule data to either check for anomalies, find correlations, or predict future sensor values.

Model 1: Heimdal: Heimdal is a program specifically tailored to pre-process sensor data and find anomalies. This model acts as a gatekeeper of sensor information. In this case 19 Airthings sensors.

Model 2: Munin: Munin combines cleaned sensor data from Heimdal with parsed conference schedule data to provide historical insights and facilitate real-time monitoring. The model aligns sensor readings with conference schedules, hoping to uncover patterns and correlations that can inform decision making processes. In essence, it is a predictor of future sensor values over time, based on attendees and that includes seasonal variations.

Model 3: Hugin: Hugin leverages the combined data processed by Heimdal and Munin to explore the feasibility of predicting the number of attendees in conference halls and meeting rooms based on sensor data. This is more of an experimental model, where linear and nonlinear algorithms are tested to see if the algorithms actually can predict attendees numbers.

5. Data warehouse details

5.1 Data sources:

The data for this study is sourced from historical sensor readings and conference schedules. Historical sensor data was collected from 19 Airthings sensors located in conference halls, meeting rooms and dining rooms, with a data timespan of 1 year, and sensor measurement intervals every 2 minutes. These sensors provided comprehensive historical readings, which were extracted from CSV files. Additionally, historical conference data containing detailed schedules, conference setup, attendees etc. was extracted and parsed from the hotel's own conference pdf. This data has a timespan over 3 years.

5.2 Procurement:

Historical readings were collected from Airthings sensors via Energy Control's dashboard, ensuring comprehensive data coverage for different rooms. Each Airthings sensor has its own csv file which can be easily extracted.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J
1	recorded	CO2 ppm	HUMIDITY %	TEMP Å°C	SOUND_LEV	LIGHT %	STALE_AIR /	TRANSMISSI	VIRUS_SUR	VIRUS_RISK /10
2	2023-05-21T00:02:52	26.80	22.63			0.00				
3	2023-05-21T00:07:51	26.78	22.63			0.00				
4	2023-05-21T00:12:51	26.93	22.63			0.00				
5	2023-05-21T00:17:50	26.76	22.65			0.00				
6	2023-05-21T00:47:00	26.92	22.63			0.00				
7	2023-05-21T00:27:50	26.97	22.63			0.00				
8	2023-05-21T00:32:51	26.92	22.63			0.00				
9	2023-05-21T00:37:50		27.apr	22.63		0.00				
10	2023-05-21T00:42:51	27.00		22.63		0.00				
11	2023-05-21T00:47:50		27.jun	22.63		0.00				
12	2023-05-21T00:52:51		27.mai	22.65		0.00				
13	2023-05-21T00:57:51		27.nov	22.63		0.00				
14	2023-05-21T01:02:52	27.13		22.50		0.00				
15	2023-05-21T01:07:51		27.sep	22.63		0.00				
16	2023-05-21T01:12:52	27.21		22.63		0.00				
17	2023-05-21T01:17:51	27.25		22.63		0.00				
18	2023-05-21T01:46:00	27.31		22.50		0.00				
19	2023-05-21T01:27:51	27.21		22.63		0.00				
20	2023-05-21T01:32:51	27.34		22.63		0.00				
21	2023-05-21T01:37:50	27.24		22.56		0.00				
22	2023-05-21T01:42:51	27.33		22.37		0.00				
23	2023-05-21T01:47:50	27.33		22.31		0.00				
24	2023-05-21T01:52:51	27.34		22.37		0.00				
25	2023-05-21T01:57:50	27.28		22.50		0.00				
26	2023-05-21T02:02:51	27.40		22.37		0.00				
27	2023-05-21T02:07:51	27.48		22.63		0.00				

Figure 2: CSV files from Airthings-sensors in its original form

Information on conferences and attendees' details was obtained from PDFs, which was then parsed and processed into usable data.

Tuesday, 16-APR-2024							
Property	Event	Time	Doorcard	Function room	Account Name	Attendees	Setup
SUND	Møte	08:30-16:30	Dronning Tyras Båttorer	Prinsen	Dronning Tyras Båttforening	7	Styrebord
SUND	Møte	08:30-16:30	Norsvin	Kroksgogen	Norsvin	27	Gruppebord a 8 pax
SUND	Møtestart med underholdning	10:00-17:30	Statsforvalteren i Oslo o	Kongressal 1+2	Statsforvalteren i Oslo og Viken	146	Gruppebord a 6 pax
SUND	Møte + rigging	13:00-22:00	NTL NAV	Dronning Åsta	NTL NAV	25	Klasserom
SUND	Grupperom	13:00-20:00	NTL NAV	Styrom 1	NTL NAV	5	Styrebord
SUND	Grupperom	15:00-19:00	Statsforvalteren i Oslo o	Prinsesse 1	Statsforvalteren i Oslo og Viken	2	Ikke avtalt
SUND	Grupperom	15:00-16:30	Statsforvalteren i Oslo o	K3 Halldan Svarte	Statsforvalteren i Oslo og Viken	60	Gruppebord a 6 pax
SUND	Møte	15:00-19:00	Ullensaker Kommune	Prinsesse 2	Ullensaker Kommune	2	Ikke avtalt
SUND	Møte	17:00-19:30	Hole Kommune	SH 1	Hole Kommune	100	Gruppebord a 8 pax
Wednesday, 17-APR-2024							
Property	Event	Time	Doorcard	Function room	Account Name	Attendees	Setup
SUND	Møte	08:00-17:30	Norconsult Norge AS	Johan Borgen	Norconsult Norge AS	10	Styrebord
SUND	Møte	08:30-11:30	Fagforbundet	Gildehuset	Fagforbundet	30	U-bord
SUND	Møte	08:30-16:30	Dronning Tyras Båttorer	Prinsen	Dronning Tyras Båttforening	7	Styrebord
SUND	Merkes: MT RDS - Topigs Norsvin	08:30-12:00	Norsvin	Styrom 4	Norsvin	5	Styrebord
SUND	Møte	08:30-17:00	Norsvin	Kroksgogen	Norsvin	28	Gruppebord a 8 pax
SUND	Møte	08:30-17:00	Bærum kommune	Krokkleiva	Bærum kommune	4	Styrebord
SUND	Grupperom	09:00-12:00	Statsforvalteren i Oslo o	Prinsesse 1	Statsforvalteren i Oslo og Viken	2	Ikke avtalt
SUND	Grupperom	09:00-12:30	Fagforbundet	Styrom 1	Fagforbundet	10	Styrebord
SUND	Grupperom	09:00-12:30	Fagforbundet	Styrom 2	Fagforbundet	10	Styrebord
SUND	Grupperom	09:00-12:30	Fagforbundet	Styrom 3	Fagforbundet	10	Styrebord
SUND	Møte	09:00-14:00	Statsforvalteren i Oslo o	Kongressal 1+2	Statsforvalteren i Oslo og Viken	139	Gruppebord a 6 pax
SUND	Møte	09:00-12:00	Ullensaker Kommune	Prinsesse 2	Ullensaker Kommune	2	Ikke avtalt
SUND	Møte	13:15-19:00	NTL NAV	Dronningsalen	NTL NAV	130	Klasserom
Thursday, 18-APR-2024							
Property	Event	Time	Doorcard	Function room	Account Name	Attendees	Setup
SUND	Møte	08:15-14:00	Norconsult Norge AS	Johan Borgen	Norconsult Norge AS	10	Styrebord
SUND	Møte	08:30-16:30	Dronning Tyras Båttorer	Prinsen	Dronning Tyras Båttforening	7	Styrebord

Figure 3: The conference pdf in its original form.

Figure 3 shows the conference event layout, which in this case does not seem to be organized in tables fit for automated data mining. In this pre-processing case, the data must be correctly extracted in text and then parsed into a csv file. This particular parsing process highlights the industry's need for ML and AI friendly ways of presenting data.

5.3 Combining data:

To create a unified dataset, historical sensor data was combined with conference data based on timestamps, room ID's and sensor ID's. This process involved aligning sensor readings with conference schedules trying to create the best circumstance for accurate correlations and analyses. Custom scripts were used to parse and process the conference data, effectively merging it with sensor data for comprehensive insights. Specifically, historically cleaned sensor data was integrated with parsed conference data, using a parsing script to convert the txt file to a CSV file. The data can now be combined into a single, cohesive dataset for analysis.

6. Interesting insights

6.1 Pdf conversion and parsing

The PDF files containing conference schedules need to be converted into text files and then parsed using scripts in PyCharm. This conversion is necessary due to the structured format of the PDF files, which require parsing to extract relevant data accurately.

6.2 Noisy data

The sensor CSV files contain [noisy data](#), with some cells having non-numerical values, such as dates in the “HUMIDITY %” column which can be seen in Figure 2. Identifying and handling these anomalies is crucial for accurate analysis.

6.3 Temporal alignment

By aligning sensor data with conference schedules based on timestamps, we can observe patterns in temperature, humidity, and Co2 levels during different events. This alignment can highlight how environmental conditions vary with room occupancy and setup.

6.4 Room and sensor ID correlation

Combining data based on room and sensor ID allows for a detailed analysis of each specific room’s environmental conditions during various conferences and activities. This can help in understanding how different setups impact air quality and comfort.

6.5 Data cleaning:

The necessity for data cleaning is evident, as the sensor data includes inconsistent formats and missing values. Standardizing the column names, converting data types, and handling missing or failing values are essential steps to prepare the data for further analysis.

Additionally, applying [Principal Component Analysis\(PCA\)](#) helps in reducing the dimensionality of the data, making it more manageable and improving the performance of subsequent machine learning algorithms.

7. Data pre-processing

7.1 Heimdal and Munin

The following table illustrates the pre-processing steps of each model with respective motivations for why this was necessary.

Table 1: Preprocessing of models

Models	Pre processing	Why?
Heimdal	<p>Based on historical csv data</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Standardizing column names • Converting datatypes (f.ex date, time and numerical values) • Ignoring or removing rows with failing values. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Standardizing column names ensures consistency across datasets, making it easier to merge and analyse data from one or multiple sources without error or confusion. • Converting data types ensures that data is in the correct format for analysis and processing. Proper data types allow for accurate calculations and comparisons, which is crucial for reliable results • Ignoring or removing rows with missing or failing values improves the quality and accuracy of the dataset. Rows missing or incorrect values can lead to misleading results and inaccuracies in the model
Munin	<p>Combining historical csv data with parsed-processed conference data, and provide historical data-insight through sensor value predictions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Parsing relevant data from conference txt.file 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Parsing relevant data from the conference was done because of insufficient data conversion from conference pdf to csv. Essentially restructuring the relevant data from the conference pdf.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Processing txt.files and creating a combined csv based on Heimdals clean data + the parsed conference data. • Standardizing and cleaning conference data to match the format of the sensor data. • Aligning sensor readings with conference schedules to ensure accurate correlations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preprocessing and combining text files and already cleansed sensor files merge multiple data sources into a single dataset, making it easier to analyze and gain insight from the combined info. • Standardizing and cleaning conference data to match csv data, ensures the combined dataset is uniform, facilitating accuracy in analysis and reducing the risk of errors due to format inconsistencies. • Aligning allows for the identification of patterns and relationships between environmental conditions and conference events, which is essential for predictive analysis and optimizing conference setups.
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8. Measuring performance

8.1 Precision

This metric measures the proportion of true positive events among all events that the model has classified as positive (Powers, 2011).

$$Precision = \frac{True\ positives}{True\ positives + False\ Negatives}$$

True positives: The number of correct positive predictions

False positives: The number of incorrect predictions

Precision was selected for its provision of insight into the accuracy of the model in identifying true anomalies without raising false alarms. For Heimdal, which acts as a gatekeeper of information, high precision ensures that only true threats or anomalies are flagged. This reduces the number of false positives that can disrupt the system or lead to unnecessary investigations (Sokolova & Lapalme, 2009). This function mirrors the role of Agent Smith in “The Matrix”.

8.2 Recall:

This metric measures the proportion of actual positive events that the model successfully identified. It is calculated as:

$$Recall = \frac{True\ positives}{True\ positives + False\ negatives}$$

True positives: The number of correct positive predictions

False negatives: The number of incorrect negative predictions

Recall was chosen because it indicates the model’s ability to detect all actual anomalies. For Heimdal, ensuring high recall is crucial to capture all potential threats or anomalies, thereby fulfilling its role as an effective outlier sentinel guarding the system against unrecognized intrusions or faults. Recall therefore reflects Heimdal’s ability to be comprehensive in detecting anomalies/outliers (Sokolova & Lapalme, 2009).

It could seem that Precision and Recall are the same, but precision focuses on the quality of the positive predictions. It provides information about how many of the predicted positive cases are actually positive. Recall on the other hand focuses on the quantity of the positive cases that the model can capture. It provides information about how many of the actual positive cases the model correctly identifies.

8.3 F1-score

This metric is the harmonic mean of precision and recall, providing a single measure that balances both, and provides a combined performance measurement.

$$F1score = 2 \times \frac{Precision \times Recall}{Precision + Recall}$$

The F1-score ranges from 0 to, where 1 indicates perfect precision and recall. The F1-score is especially valuable in scenarios where class distribution is imbalanced and need to consider both false positives and false negatives.

The F1-score was selected because it combines both precision and recall into a single metric, offering a more comprehensive measure of the model's performance. This metric is especially useful when there is an imbalance between classes as it offers a more balanced evaluation of performance (Chicco & Jurman, 2020). For Heimdal, achieving a balance between detecting all anomalies (high recall) and ensuring that detected anomalies are genuine (high precision) is critical. The F1-score helps in evaluating the model's overall effectiveness in maintaining this balance.

Relevance to Heimdal's role and purpose: Heimdal's task as an anomaly detection system is akin to being the gatekeeper of information. Its primary role is to ensure the integrity and security of the system by identifying and flagging anomalies that could indicate potential threats or faults. The selected metrics- precision, recall and F1-score- reflects this dual responsibility.

To sum up the measuring metrics for the model Heimdal:

- Precision ensures that Heimdal minimizes false alarms, maintaining system stability
- Recall guarantees comprehensive detection of all potential anomalies, safeguarding against undetected threats
- F1 score offers a balanced evaluation of both precision and recall, ensuring Heimdal's efficiency in its gatekeeping role

In this particular case, outliers or anomalies in sensor data are detected from conference halls and meeting rooms such as high deviating temperature, co2 levels and humidity. Modern machine learning algorithms play a vital role. One particularly effective method in this case is the Local Outlier Factor, which has potential to be very accurate on datasets such as historic sensor data from Airthings.

8.4 Mean squared error(MSE):

Mean squared error (MSE) measures the average squared difference between the actual values and predicted value (Wilmott & Matsuura, 2005). It gives an idea of how close the predictions are to the actual values.

$$MSE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2$$

y_i = The actual value

\hat{y}_i = The predicted values

n = The number of observations

MSE was selected because it heavily penalizes larger errors, providing a clear measure of how well the model's predictions match the actual values. This metric is crucial for understanding the accuracy of predictions in continuous data scenarios such as temperature, humidity and Co2 levels.

8.5 Mean absolute error (MAE)

Mean absolute error measures the average absolute difference between the actual values and the predicted values, without squaring the errors (Wilmott & Matsuura, 2005). When compared to MSE, it does not square the difference, so it treats all errors **equally**.

$$MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |y_i - \hat{y}_i|$$

MAE was chosen because it provides a straightforward measure of the average error in predictions, making it easier to interpret. It is particularly useful when understanding the average magnitude of prediction errors in the same unit as the data.

8.6 R-squared(R^2)

R-squared(R^2), also known as the coefficient of determination, measures the proportion of the variance in the dependent variables that is predictable from the independent variables(Nagelkerke, 1991). It provides an indication of how well the model explains the variability of the outcome.

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2}$$

R² was selected because it indicates the explanatory power of the model. A higher R² value means that the model can explain more of the variability in the outcome variable. This makes it a key metric for evaluating the performance of regression models.

8.7 Metric essence and specific use case

Precision tells us how many of the positive predictions made by the model were actually correct. In Heimdal's anomaly detection, high precision ensures that when the model flags an anomaly, it is very likely to be a true anomaly. This reduces unnecessary alerts and investigations, maintaining operational efficiency. For example, being able to recognize an anomaly like a human actively breathing on sensors to spike Co2 levels.

Recall tells us how many of the actual positives cases were correctly identified by the model. For Heimdal, high recall ensures that all potential anomalies are detected, even if it means flagging some false positives. This is essential in maintaining system integrity and security by ensuring no potential threat goes unnoticed. For instance, detecting all instances of high or low humidity that might indicate a malfunctioning HVACR system.

F1-score combines Precision and Recall into a single measure. For Heimdal, the F1-score offers a comprehensive measure of the model's effectiveness in detecting anomalies, ensuring that the system is both accurate and comprehensive in its anomaly detection. This is crucial for maintaining a stable and secure environment, such as ensuring that temperature anomalies are detected without overwhelming the system with false positives.

MSE measures the average of the squares of the errors, giving more weight to larger errors. In Munin's historical analysis and Hugin's predictive analysis, MSE provides a clear measure of how closely the model's predictions match the actual sensor readings and conference data. Models with lower MSE values indicate more accurate predictions, which is crucial for reliable forecasting of environmental conditions in conference and meeting rooms. For example, accurately predicting future Co2 levels based on historical data helps in adjusting ventilation in advance (ventilation planning) and tailors the ventilation to the occupants needs and at the same time reducing energy consumption without jeopardizing IAQ (indoor air quality).

MAE measures the average of the absolute errors, providing a straightforward measure of prediction accuracy. For Hugin and Munin, MAE helps in understanding the average magnitude of errors in the model's predictions. This is particularly useful for understanding day to day variations in temperature, humidity and CO2 levels, assisting in making automatic

fine-tuned adjustments to the HVACR system. For example, ensuring that the predicted temperature aligns closely with the actual room temperature to maintain guest comfort.

R^2 quantifies the proportion of variance in the dependent variable that can be explained by the independent variables. In simpler terms, it shows how effectively the model identifies the relationships within the data. In Munin, R^2 provides insights into how well the model explains the variability of the target, which is variables such as temperature, attendees, humidity, CO2 etc. For example, a high R^2 close to 1) indicates high predictive ability and reflects how well the model can forecast future outcomes.

9. Applied models and algorithms

For this project the algorithms applied for each model varies with their purpose. Therefore, the algorithms presented in this section will briefly discuss each algorithm applied, then highlight the best performing algorithm for each model.

9.1 Outlier/Anomaly checker Heimdal:

9.1.1 Local outlier factor (LOF)

The local outlier factor algorithm assesses the local deviation of a data point in relation to its neighbouring points. It assigns an anomaly score to each data point based on how isolated the point is compared to its surrounding points. LOF is particularly effective in detecting anomalies in datasets with variable density.

LOF was selected because it excels in detecting anomalies in complex datasets where datapoints may exhibit varying densities. This characteristic is particularly useful for sensor data from the hotel, where readings can vary significantly based on room occupancy and environmental conditions.

9.1.2 Random Forest

Random forest is an [ensemble learning method](#) that constructs multiple decision trees during the training phase and then aggregates their outputs to make final predictions. For regression tasks, it computes the mean prediction of the individual trees, while for classification, it takes the mode of the classes. It is robust to [overfitting](#) and is known for often providing good accuracy.

Random forest was chosen for its robustness, especially when working with high-dimensional data. It can capture complex interactions between features, which is advantageous for outlier and anomaly detection in sensor data with numerous variables. Furthermore, Random Forest

can manage large amount of [noise](#) and missing data by creating diverse decision trees based on different subsets of the training data, resulting in a more generalized and reliable model. This flexibility, combined with its ability to reduce variance through bagging, enhances its performance in both regression and classification tasks.

Figure 4: The diagram illustrates the structure of a Random Forest algorithm, consisting of multiple decision trees. Each tree is trained separately on the same dataset, and the final prediction is obtained by combining the predictions from all trees using mode for classification and mean for regression.

9.1.3 Isolation Forest

Isolation Forest is an effective anomaly/outlier detection algorithm that isolates data points by randomly selecting features and splitting them at random values between their minimum and maximum. This process is repeated to construct decision trees, where anomalies are quicker to isolate because they differ significantly from the majority of the data. The algorithm recursively partitions the data until all observations are isolated.

Isolation Forest was selected for its efficiency and effectiveness in detecting anomalies in large datasets. It is particularly useful for datasets where the anomalies are few and different.

9.1.4 KMeans Clustering

KMeans clustering is an unsupervised learning algorithm that divides data into K-clusters. Each data point is assigned to the cluster with the closest mean, and the algorithm continuously adjusts the cluster centres to minimize the variance within each cluster.

KMeans was selected for its simplicity and effectiveness in partitioning data into distinct clusters. By identifying the clusters, anomalies can be detected as data points that do not fit well into any cluster.

9.1.5 Training and testing Heimdall's algorithms

To ensure the reliability and accuracy of the models, the algorithms are trained, tested and validated. This involved splitting the dataset (in this case csv files) into training and testing sets, training the model on the training set and then evaluating the model on the testing set using metrics like precision, recall and F1-score.

Heimdall's process:

- Load and preprocess sensor data from csv files
- Standardizing column names (due to problems with reading and registering the csv file correctly)
- Convert relevant columns to numeric types and handle missing values
- Data splitting
- Model training

- Testing and evaluating results

9.1.6 Heimdal's code:

Necessary libraries:

```
import os
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
import joblib
from sklearn.ensemble import IsolationForest, RandomForestClassifier
from sklearn.neighbors import LocalOutlierFactor
from sklearn.cluster import KMeans
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from sklearn.metrics import precision_score, recall_score, f1_score
```

Code snippet 1: The necessary libraries required for Heimdals ML-pipeline, including tools for data manipulation, model training and performance evaluation.

Training:

```
# Funksjoner for å trene modeller
def train_isolation_forest(data):
    print("Trener Isolation Forest...")
    iso_forest = IsolationForest(contamination='auto', random_state=42)
    iso_forest.fit(data)
    joblib.dump(iso_forest, 'models/heimdal_isolation_forest.pkl')
    return iso_forest

def train_lof(data):
    print("Trener Local Outlier Factor...")
    lof = LocalOutlierFactor(n_neighbors=20, novelty=True)
    lof.fit(data)
    joblib.dump(lof, 'models/heimdal_lof.pkl')
    return lof

def train_kmeans(data):
    print("Trener KMeans...")
    kmeans = KMeans(n_clusters=3, random_state=42)
    kmeans.fit(data)
    joblib.dump(kmeans, 'models/heimdal_kmeans.pkl')
    return kmeans

def train_random_forest(data, labels):
```

```

print("Trener Random Forest...")
random_forest = RandomForestClassifier(random_state=42, n_jobs=-1)
random_forest.fit(data, labels)
joblib.dump(random_forest, 'models/heimdal_random_forest.pkl')
return random_forest

```

Code snippet 2: Functions to train different models (applied algorithms). Each model is trained on provided data and saved for future testing.

Testing:

```

def test_models(data, labels):
    iso_forest = joblib.load('models/heimdal_isolation_forest.pkl')
    lof = joblib.load('models/heimdal_lof.pkl')
    kmeans = joblib.load('models/heimdal_kmeans.pkl')
    random_forest = joblib.load('models/heimdal_random_forest.pkl')

    iso_forest_preds = iso_forest.predict(data)
    lof_preds = lof.predict(data)
    kmeans_preds = kmeans.predict(data)
    random_forest_preds = random_forest.predict(data)

    # Konverter -1 og 1 til 0 og 1 for konsistens i ytelsesmålinger
    iso_forest_preds = np.where(iso_forest_preds == -1, 0, 1)
    lof_preds = np.where(lof_preds == -1, 0, 1)

    print("Isolation Forest Metrics:")
    print(f"Precision: {precision_score(labels, iso_forest_preds):.2f}")
    print(f"Recall: {recall_score(labels, iso_forest_preds):.2f}")
    print(f"F1 Score: {f1_score(labels, iso_forest_preds):.2f}\n")

    print("Local Outlier Factor Metrics:")
    print(f"Precision: {precision_score(labels, lof_preds):.2f}")
    print(f"Recall: {recall_score(labels, lof_preds):.2f}")
    print(f"F1 Score: {f1_score(labels, lof_preds):.2f}\n")

    print("KMeans Metrics:")
    unique, counts = np.unique(kmeans_preds, return_counts=True)
    smallest_cluster = unique[np.argmin(counts)]
    kmeans_outliers = np.where(kmeans_preds == smallest_cluster, 1, 0)
    print(f"Precision: {precision_score(labels, kmeans_outliers):.2f}")
    print(f"Recall: {recall_score(labels, kmeans_outliers):.2f}")
    print(f"F1 Score: {f1_score(labels, kmeans_outliers):.2f}\n")

    print("Random Forest Metrics:")
    print(f"Precision: {precision_score(labels, random_forest_preds):.2f}")
    print(f"Recall: {recall_score(labels, random_forest_preds):.2f}")
    print(f"F1 Score: {f1_score(labels, random_forest_preds):.2f}\n")

```

Code snippet 3: This function tests the trained models by loading them from saved files and evaluating their performance using metrics like precision, recall and F1-score.

Notable comments:

- Using `random_state=42` ensures that the results are reproducible. This parameter helps to produce the same train-test-split and model results every time the code is run. This makes it easier to debug and compare results across different runs.
- KMeans require additional steps in testing because it does not inherently classify data points as outliers. Instead, we need to determine which cluster represents outliers. This is done by identifying the smallest cluster (the one with fewest datapoints) and marking these points as outliers. This extra step is needed for KMeans to be comparable to the other algorithms.
- Algorithmic efficiency is also notable. Isolation Forest and Local Outlier Factor are particularly useful for high dimensional data and datasets with varying density, respectively. Random Forest, while effective, can be computationally intensive and may require optimization for larger datasets.

9.1.7 Heimdal’s results

The processing results from 19 sensors with a data timespan of 1 year (2023-2024) and measurement intervals every 2 minutes for temperature and humidity, and every 6 minutes for Co2:

Table 2: Heimdal’s result and comments for each applied algorithm

Algorithm	Metrics: Precision, Recall, F1-score	Comments
Local Outlier Factor	Precision: 0.95 Recall: 1.00 F1-score: 0.97	Perfect recall (100%) means all true outliers were detected, and precision remains high (95%) indicating few false positives.
Isolation Forest	Precision:0.95 Recall: 0.87 F1-score: 0.91	High precision (95%) indicates that most of identified outliers are actual outliers. The recall (87%) is

		slightly lower suggesting some true outliers were missed.
KMeans	Precision: 0.95 Recall: 0.02 F1-score: 0.04	Despite high precision (95%), the very low recall (2%) indicates a failing in identifying true outliers.
Random Forest	Precision: 0.95 Recall: 1.00 F1-score: 0.97	Similar to Local Outlier Factor. Making it highly effective for outlier detection in this dataset.

The table clearly shows that Local outlier factor and Random Forest (with F1-scores at 97%) are the best algorithms for outlier detection in the case of analysing csv data from 19 sensors. The most effective is Local Outlier Factor due to shorter training duration. Random forest spent about 1 minute and 40 seconds to process and train, while Local Outlier Factor only spent about 5 seconds to process and train. This amplifies the point of applying an ML algorithm with respect to the specific task it is supposed to do, which in this case is a fast and accurate anomaly and outlier detection. For example, Random Forest, could have been reduced to fewer decision trees in order to speed up training time, but could have produced less satisfying results.

9.2 Munin- Combinator of cleaned data and predicator of sensor values based on attendees.

9.2.1 SARIMA:

SARIMA (Seasonal Auto Regressive Integrated Moving Average) is an enhancement of the ARIMA model, designed specifically for time series data with a clear seasonal component. It includes mechanisms for autoregressive differencing, and moving average, combined with seasonal adjustments, making it a robust choice for time series forecasting with respect to seasonality.

Given the historical nature of the data from Munin, which includes seasonal variations in conference and meeting room usage, SARIMA can in theory capture and forecast these periodic trends accurately.

9.2.2 LSTM:

Long term short memory or LSTM is a type of recurrent neural network(RNN) that is specifically built to to capture long term dependencies in sequential data. It is particularly effective for time series forecasting, as it can retain and utilize information over long time periods, and manage complex non-linear relationships.

LSTM was selected for its ability to handle complex and long-term patterns in time series data. Figure 3 illustrates the basic structure of LSTM neural network. The network consists of multiple layers and nodes, connected in a specific manner to facilitate the processing and retention of sequential data, much like a natural occurring brain connection when humans learn a specific new type of skill.

Long / Short Term Memory (LSTM)

Figure 5: A visual representation of the recurrent neural network LSTM

The input layer (yellow nodes) receives the input data. In time series forecasting, these inputs could be historical values of the variable being predicted, in this case temperature, Co2 and humidity from csv files. The blue nodes are hidden layers, which contain the LSTM units, which are the core components of the network. Each LSTM unit has a cell state and various gates (input, output and forget gates) that regulate the flow of information and

maintain long term-dependencies. The red nodes are the output layers, providing the final predictions or outputs of the network.

9.2.3 Random Forest

As stated earlier, Random Forest is an ensemble learning method, that constructs multiple decision trees during training. It provides predictions by averaging the outcomes for regression tasks or selecting the mode for classification tasks. In this case Random Forest was chosen in this case based on curiosity to see how well it performs under different circumstances/when applied to a new type of task.

9.2.4 Training and testing Munin's algorithms

To ensure the reliability and accuracy of the models, the algorithms are trained, tested and validated in two different tests. In Munin's case, the measuring metrics are MSE, MAE and R-squared.

Munin's process:

- Loading and preprocessing cleaned CSV data from Heimdal
- Combining parsed data with sensor data. Including manual cleaning and PCA (Principal Component Analysis) in test 2 to further optimize

9.2.5 Munin's Code

The following code is from Munin's second test, after manual cleaning and applied PCA. The pseudocodes mark the beginning of the training and testing code for the respective algorithms.

Necessary libraries:

```
import os
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
import joblib
from pmdarima.arima import auto_arima
from tensorflow.keras.models import Sequential, load_model
from tensorflow.keras.layers import LSTM, Dense
from sklearn.ensemble import RandomForestRegressor
from sklearn.preprocessing import StandardScaler
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from sklearn.metrics import mean_squared_error, mean_absolute_error, r2_score
import time
```

Code snippet 4: This snippet imports the needed libraries for Munins ML-pipeline, including tools for data handling, model training, neural network construction and performance evaluation.

Training:

```
# Train SARIMA model
def train_sarima(data):
    print("Training SARIMA...")
    start_time = time.time()
    if data.shape[0] < 20:
        raise ValueError("Not enough data points to train SARIMA model.")

    model = auto_arima(data['PC1'], seasonal=True, m=12, stepwise=True, suppress_warnings=True,
max_order=10)
    joblib.dump(model, 'models/munin_sarima.pkl')

    end_time = time.time()
    elapsed_time = end_time - start_time
    print(f"SARIMA model training completed in {elapsed_time:.2f} seconds.")
    return model

# Train LSTM model
def train_lstm(data):
    print("Training LSTM...")
    start_time = time.time()

    scaler = StandardScaler()
    scaled_data = scaler.fit_transform(data[['PC1', 'PC2', 'PC3', 'PC4', 'Attendees']])

    X = []
    y = []
    time_step = 10
    for i in range(time_step, len(scaled_data)):
        X.append(scaled_data[i - time_step:i])
        y.append(scaled_data[i, 0])

    X, y = np.array(X), np.array(y)
    X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(X, y, test_size=0.2, random_state=42)

    model = Sequential()
    model.add(LSTM(units=50, return_sequences=True, input_shape=(X_train.shape[1], X_train.shape[2])))
    model.add(LSTM(units=50))
    model.add(Dense(1))
    model.compile(optimizer='adam', loss='mean_squared_error')
    model.fit(X_train, y_train, epochs=20, batch_size=32, validation_data=(X_test, y_test))

    model.save('models/munin_lstm.h5')
    joblib.dump(scaler, 'models/munin_scaler.pkl')
    end_time = time.time()
```

```

elapsed_time = end_time - start_time
print(f"LSTM model training completed in {elapsed_time:.2f} seconds.")
return model, scaler

# Train Random Forest model
def train_random_forest(data):
    print("Training Random Forest...")
    start_time = time.time()

    labels = data['PC1']
    features = data.drop(['PC1', 'Recorded', 'Time', 'Sensor ID', 'Setup', 'DayOfWeek', 'Hour'], axis=1)
    X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(features, labels, test_size=0.2, random_state=42)

    model = RandomForestRegressor(random_state=42, n_jobs=-1)
    model.fit(X_train, y_train)
    joblib.dump(model, 'models/munin_random_forest.pkl')
    end_time = time.time()
    elapsed_time = end_time - start_time
    print(f"Random Forest model training completed in {elapsed_time:.2f} seconds.")
    return model

```

Code snippet 5: This snippet includes the training functions for the SARIMA, LSTM and Random Forest models. Each function trains its respective model using the dataset and saves the trained model for future testing.

Testing:

```

# Test models and output metrics
def test_models(data):
    # Test SARIMA model
    sarima_model = joblib.load('models/munin_sarima.pkl')
    sarima_predictions = sarima_model.predict(n_periods=len(data))
    sarima_mse = mean_squared_error(data['PC1'], sarima_predictions)
    sarima_mae = mean_absolute_error(data['PC1'], sarima_predictions)
    sarima_r2 = r2_score(data['PC1'], sarima_predictions)

    print("SARIMA Model Metrics:")
    print(f"Mean Squared Error: {sarima_mse}")
    print(f"Mean Absolute Error: {sarima_mae}")
    print(f"R-squared: {sarima_r2}")

    # Test LSTM model
    lstm_model = load_model('models/munin_lstm.h5')
    scaler = joblib.load('models/munin_scaler.pkl')
    scaled_data = scaler.transform(data[['PC1', 'PC2', 'PC3', 'PC4', 'Attendees']])

    X = []
    y = []
    time_step = 10
    for i in range(time_step, len(scaled_data)):
        X.append(scaled_data[i - time_step:i])

```

```

y.append(scaled_data[i, 0])

X, y = np.array(X), np.array(y)
lstm_predictions = lstm_model.predict(X)
lstm_mse = mean_squared_error(y, lstm_predictions)
lstm_mae = mean_absolute_error(y, lstm_predictions)
lstm_r2 = r2_score(y, lstm_predictions)

print("LSTM Model Metrics:")
print(f"Mean Squared Error: {lstm_mse}")
print(f"Mean Absolute Error: {lstm_mae}")
print(f"R-squared: {lstm_r2}")

# Test Random Forest model
rf_model = joblib.load('models/munin_random_forest.pkl')
labels = data['PC1']
features = data.drop(['PC1', 'Recorded', 'Time', 'Sensor ID', 'Setup', 'DayOfWeek', 'Hour'], axis=1)
rf_predictions = rf_model.predict(features)
rf_mse = mean_squared_error(labels, rf_predictions)
rf_mae = mean_absolute_error(labels, rf_predictions)
rf_r2 = r2_score(labels, rf_predictions)

print("Random Forest Model Metrics:")
print(f"Mean Squared Error: {rf_mse}")
print(f"Mean Absolute Error: {rf_mae}")
print(f"R-squared: {rf_r2}")

```

Code snippet 6: This function tests the trained models by loading them from saved files and evaluating their performance using metrics like mean squared error (MSE), mean absolute error (MAE) and R-squared (R^2).

Notable comments:

- Using `auto_arima`, with a specified random state ensures that the model's parameter selection is consistent across different runs.
- Time series models like SARIMA and LSTM require a large historical data baseline to forecast effectively, reflecting the need for a well-defined dataset, especially when seasonal patterns are considered. Because the sensor data is from a 1-year time span, the conditions for accurate time series prediction, decreases.

9.2.6 Munin's results

The first test result for Munin: data size reduction and sampling size are used for faster training time (given that SARIMA and LSTM can spend up to several hours of training).

Table 3: Munin's results and comments for each applied algorithm

Algorithm	Metrics: MSE, MAE, R-squared	Comments
SARIMA	MSE: 0.825, MAE: 0.699, R ² : -0.0009	Moderate MSE and MAE, but low R ² value. Indicates that SARIMA did not perform well in capturing the variability in the dataset, likely due to insufficient data size.
LSTM	MSE: 2.299, MAE 1.168, R ² : -1.386	The high MSE and MAE. Along with a negative R ² suggest that the LSTM model struggled significantly with the reduced dataset, failing to capture the complex relationship.
Random Forest	MSE: 0.733, MAE: 0.653, R ² : 0.112	Performed relatively better, with the highest R ² but still not ideal. It managed to capture more variance compared to SARIMA and LSTM

The reduced dataset for faster training resulted in poorer metrics

In order to enhance the performance, we need to re-preprocess the parsed conference data csv file as well as the combined data, to remove further noise, shorten training duration and hopefully get better results. This involves applying PCA(Principal Component Analysis) to further optimize the data.

After further cleaning and noise removal from the combined dataset, here are the results for Munins 2nd test:

Table 4: Munin's result after dataset/preprocessing improvement

Algorithm	Metrics: MSE, MAE, R ²	Comments
SARIMA	MSE: 1.255	SARIMA showed moderate MSE and MAE but a very low R ² . This

	MAE: 0.9 R ² :-0.000007	suggests that SARIMA struggled with the reduced dataset size, failing to model the complex relationships adequately.
LSTM	MSE: 0.969 MAE: 0.789 R ² : 0.031	LSTM performed better than SARIMA with lower MSE and MAE, and a slightly positive R ² value, indicating it managed to capture some of the data's complexity. However, its performance is still not ideal, suggesting room for improvement with more data or fine tuning.
Random Forest	MSE:0.12 MAE: 0.203 R ² : 0.904	Random Forest significantly outperformed the other models, achieving the lowest MSE and MAE and a high R ² value of 0.904. This indicates that the Random Forest model was able to capture the majority of the variance in the data and model the relationships effectively, even with the reduced dataset.

Munin's second test shows notable improvements across the algorithms after preprocessing further through data cleaning, noise removal and applying PCA to optimize data handling.

Data reduction was essential for reducing training time and processing power. However, the reduction in data size led to poorer performance in SARIMA and LSTM models. This is most likely due to their sensitivity to data volume and quality, given that they require a substantial amount of data points to work accurately. Random Forest, on the other hand, handled the reduced dataset well, showing robustness and flexibility in capturing the relationships within the data. This suggests that for applications requiring quick insights with limited data, Random Forest will be the preferred choice in this case. For more detailed and nuanced forecasting, larger datasets with qualitative pre-processing might be necessary for models like SARIMA and LSTM to perform optimally.

9.3 Hugin- Predictor of attendees based on sensor values

9.3.1 Linear regression

Linear regression, while a fundamental statistical tool in predictive modelling, might not always be the most suitable choice for sensor data, particularly if the data exhibits complex patterns or non-linear relationships which is often the case for sensors.

However, testing a linear regression model can still provide valuable insights, especially as a baseline comparison for more complex models. By applying linear regression to sensor data, we can establish a straightforward understanding of the relationships within the data. This allows to quantify how much of the variance in sensor readings can be explained through linear relationships, setting a benchmark for evaluating performance of more sophisticated models like Random Forest or Neural Networks.

9.3.2 XGBoost

XGBoost (eXtreme Gradient Boosting) is an advanced implementation of gradient boosting algorithms, known for its high performance and speed in machine learning tasks. XGBoost provides a scalable and efficient solution for supervised learning problems by constructing an ensemble of decision trees in a sequential manner, where each subsequent tree model attempts to correct the errors made by the previous ones.

XGBoost was chosen for its known robustness and ability to handle diverse and large datasets effectively.

Hugin's process:

Essentially the same as Munin only trying to predict attendees based on sensor values, which is a very challenging task in the first place. Hugin's process also includes adding [hyperparameter tuning](#) to improve results.

9.3.3 Hugin's code

The following code is from Hugin's second test, where both PCA was applied and additionally hyperparameter tuning for Random Forest.

Necessary libraries:

```

import pandas as pd
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from sklearn.linear_model import LinearRegression
from sklearn.ensemble import RandomForestRegressor
from sklearn.metrics import mean_squared_error, mean_absolute_error, r2_score
import xgboost as xgb
import time
from sklearn.decomposition import PCA
from sklearn.preprocessing import StandardScaler

```

Code snippet 7: The required libraries for running Hugin

Training:

```

# Train Random Forest model with hyperparameter tuning
def train_random_forest(X_train, y_train):
    print("Training Random Forest model")
    start_time = time.time()
    rf_model = RandomForestRegressor(n_estimators=50, random_state=42, n_jobs=-1)
    rf_model.fit(X_train, y_train)
    elapsed_time = time.time() - start_time
    print(f"Random Forest model training completed in {elapsed_time:.2f} seconds.")
    return rf_model

# Train Linear Regression model
def train_linear_regression(X_train, y_train):
    print("Training Linear Regression model")
    start_time = time.time()
    lr_model = LinearRegression()
    lr_model.fit(X_train, y_train)
    elapsed_time = time.time() - start_time
    print(f"Linear Regression model training completed in {elapsed_time:.2f} seconds.")
    return lr_model

# Train XGBoost model
def train_xgboost(X_train, y_train):
    print("Training XGBoost model")
    start_time = time.time()
    xgb_model = xgb.XGBRegressor(objective='reg:squarederror', n_estimators=50, random_state=42, n_jobs=-1)
    xgb_model.fit(X_train, y_train)
    elapsed_time = time.time() - start_time
    print(f"XGBoost model training completed in {elapsed_time:.2f} seconds.")
    return xgb_model

```

Code snippet 8: Training the model using different algorithms.

Testing:

```

# Evaluate models
def evaluate_model(model, X_test, y_test, model_type='linear_regression', scaler=None):
    y_pred = model.predict(X_test)

    mse = mean_squared_error(y_test, y_pred)
    mae = mean_absolute_error(y_test, y_pred)
    r2 = r2_score(y_test, y_pred)

    print(f"{model_type.upper()} Model Metrics:")
    print(f"Mean Squared Error: {mse}")
    print(f"Mean Absolute Error: {mae}")
    print(f"R-squared: {r2}")
    print()

    return mse, mae, r2

```

Code snippet 9: The code required for testing and validation

9.3. Hugin’s results

Hugin’s first training process took a considerable amount of time and performed very poorly. Highlights for Hugin’s first couple of training tests:

Table 5: Hugin’s result from iterative testing

Algorithm	Metrics test 1 (before further data cleaning)	Metrics test 2 (after manual cleaning and PCA on combined dataset)
Random Forest	MSE: 30268.330 MAE: 332.068 R ² : -0.111	MSE: 3042.283 MAE: 33.662 R ² : -0.117
Linear regression	MSE: 27217.731 MAE: 336.617 R ² : 0.0008	MSE: 2721.773 MAE: 33.662 R ² : 0.0008
XGBoost	MSE: 2667.213	MSE: 2681.217

	MAE: 333.492	MAE:33.443
	R ² : 0.0207	R ² : 0.0157

The table shows that MSE and MAE for all models decreased significantly, by approximately ten times after manual cleaning and PCA. Despite the improvements, the model performance remains suboptimal, with R² values close to zero or negative, indicating that a simple linear model would be more effective in capturing the data variability.

The current algorithms are not well suited for this specific task, given the poor performance metrics even after further data cleaning and PCA. Predicting attendee numbers based on sensor data proves to be inherently more challenging than predicting sensor values from known attendee counts, due to the complex and indirect relationships involved.

10. Discussion

10.1 Heimdal: A gatekeeper and preparator of sensor data

Heimdal, designed specifically for analyzing sensor data, demonstrated outstanding performance with high accuracy, recall and F1-score. These metrics indicate Heimdal's ability to not only correctly identify true positives, but also to minimize false negatives, thereby ensuring comprehensive anomaly detection. The two best performing algorithms LOF and Random Forest had an F1-score at 0.97 or 97%, and further emphasizes the model's balance between precision and recall. This makes it exceptionally reliable in real world scenarios. Heimdal's effectiveness in handling sensor data makes it ideal for applications in smart buildings, industrial monitoring, and any environment where precise sensor data analysis is critical for operational safety and efficiency.

10.2 Munin: Bridging the gap with significant improvements

Munin, which combines sensor data with conference data to predict sensor values based on attendees, initially demonstrated moderate to low performance. In the first test, despite reasonable MSE and MAE levels, the models struggled with capturing the variance, as indicated by R² scores close to zero or negative. Specifically, SARIMA and LSTM showed limited capabilities in managing the complexities of the reduced dataset, highlighting their need for more extensive data and longer seasonal spans to function properly.

However, significant improvements were observed in the second testing phase after additional data cleaning, noise removal and the application of Principal Component Analysis(PCA). Here, Random Forest outperformed the other models with an impressive MSE

of 0.12, MAE of 0.203 and an R^2 of 0.904. This demonstrates that Random Forest could effectively capture the majority of the variance in the data, modelling the relationships within it effectively, even with the dataset constraints.

The performance of Random Forest in the second test underscores its robustness and adaptability to varying data quality and size, making it a particularly valuable model for applications requiring rapid insight from limited datasets. Meanwhile, SARIMA and LSTM showed marginal improvements, their performance remains a work in progress, indicating a need for richer datasets and perhaps more qualitative pre-processing and fine-tuning to truly excel.

Munin's capability to handle and process multifaceted data makes it a viable solution for scenarios that require moderate complexity and data integration. This balanced approach is well-suited for applications where a certain degree of data diversity is essential but without the need for extensive integration complexity. For instance, an evolved version of Munin could be effectively employed in environments where additional contextual information is crucial to enhance decision-making processes. This includes medium-complexity smart systems or integrated monitoring setups, where Munin's ability to integrate and analyse diverse data streams can significantly improve operational intelligence and efficiency. By advancing its processing capabilities and further fine tuning its algorithms to its specific task, Munin could offer more robust support for dynamic environments that demand nuanced data-insights and rapid adaptation to changing conditions.

10.3 Hugin

Hugin's results have shown that not all algorithms perform equally well across different types of data or integration challenges. It struggled significantly even after improved pre-processing, indicating algorithmic and dataset limitation.

Furthermore, Hugin's results can be connected to emphasize the critical role of data harmonisation. Without a coherent structure and alignment of data from multiple sources, even the most sophisticated algorithms struggle to extract meaningful insights. This points to the necessity of investing in preprocessing steps that enhance data quality. From a detailed standpoint: cleaning, normalization and feature selection. From an overarching standpoint: standardizing the way of collecting different types of data to create exceptionally well cleaned datasets for a comprehensive, unified database. Such a standardized method and database for various societal districts would facilitate the availability and effectiveness of AI and ML applications, unlocking their full potential.

10.4 Circumstance adaptation and prompt engineering

When experimenting with modern ML-algorithms to evaluate their performance, one must be keen to see the different applicable scenarios for each model based on their type, processing structure etc. It is a reason it's such a common practice to choose a handful of models, and then evaluate after training and testing which model to use. Because of different datasets, databases, API-live data transmission etc, every situation is a potential unique problem that needs the right adaptation; therefore, a specific ML model might be able to execute the specific task in the specific environment more smoothly and effectively than others. This can be related to the emerging needed skill in modern AI-to-human exchange, which is prompt engineering. This is essentially the skill of giving premises that creates the needed leeway and capacity for a qualitative analysis and output. The same way you set a boundary condition/ prompt/ circumstance parameter to an LLM like GPT, the quality of the prompt decides the quality of the output. Choosing ML algorithms for different purposes like anomaly detection, historic analysis, predictive and simulative processing and display can be compared to modern AI prompt engineering, only that the prompt engineering bases itself on the prompter knowing the circumstances of the data situation. Machine learning is and has always been about using data models to extract, predict, calculate, draw, write, generate, visualize etc. in order to relieve humans of repetitive tasks that require processing power/human processing capacity. Being able to outsource needed capacity for these types of tasks can relieve humans of repetitive work while enhancing both efficiency in human-computer interaction, as well as ensuring a steady operation flow without making mistakes (if the program is written well enough). When looking at the modern world and the peak of the new technology I personally get very excited and at the same time anxious when thinking of the potential in the next 30 years of exponential AI development. Given that both ML and AI has had a recent boom in development, as well as the rest of Industry 4.0's development like Neuralink, VR/AR/XR(Virtual, augmented, eXtended reality), [IoT](#). If these technologies merge under/together with AI development, the possibility of an actual human cyborg like in the movie Terminator, would not be so far-fetched anymore.

10.5 Processing power

The development of AI has revolutionized numerous industries, offering unparalleled opportunities and efficiencies. However, one of the most pressing challenges in this advancement is the substantial need for processing power. AI models, especially those involving deep learning like LSTM, SARIMA and XGBoost, require significant computational resources for effective training. As the complexity of these models and volume of data increase, so does the demand for processing power. This raises a critical question: How can we reduce the need for processing power without compromising model performance? Technological innovations, such as optimized algorithms and data compression techniques

can enhance efficiency. Additionally, strategies like data reduction and selective data collection can mitigate the volume of data processed. For example, one of the reasons for Munin's medium performance was because of data reduction.

Beyond technological improvements, the discussion extends to energy consumption and sustainability. Running AI models, particularly in large data centers, entails considerable energy use. This shifts the focus to energy-efficient computing. Leveraging renewable energy sources, developing energy-efficient hardware, and utilizing distributed computing systems near data sources can reduce the reliance on centralized data centers and save energy. Future AI development must balance powerful, effective models with sustainable, energy-efficient practices to ensure AI's growth is economically and environmentally viable.

10.6 Modern tech development "speculation"

Based on the insights from Vinnakota's (2023) research in leveraging AI in the hospitality industry, which emphasizes the integration of AI, ML, VR etc. to improve operational efficiency, guest experience and resource management, we can forecast significant potential technological development in the next 30 years that could revolutionize the building industry and overall society.

Suggestions of modern tech development under the next 30 years with relevance to Industry 4.0, Industry 5.0, with a gradually increasing speculation level for each headline:

10.6.1 Smart glasses x IoT

Smart glasses integrated with [IoT](#) could redefine how building management systems operate. This could for example involve CFD simulations when examining the HVAC system, where the person using the smart glasses could get a live simulation of the specific component/room they want to analyze. If conference attendees were to use smart glasses integrated with CFD simulation like the one exemplified in [2.4.3](#), they could be able to tell how to organize, where to sit in order for optimal: concentration, thermal comfort, air quality preference and energy efficiency.

10.6.2: Smart watches x IoT

In the future, integrating smart watches could enhance environmental controls systems by providing real time insights and personalized preference data like PPD (predicted percentage dissatisfied). This integration would allow for dynamic monitoring of an occupant's actual need through smart watch sensor readings, enabling a precise adjustment of HVACR systems.

This approach would optimize IAQ and energy efficiency, aligning closely with demand-controlled ventilation.

10.6.3 Neuralink X ANN's

In the upcoming decades, the convergence of [ANNs](#) with biotic neural networks through technologies like Neuralink could dramatically enhance cognitive capacity and processing power. Such integrations promise a synergy that could, metaphorically, provide “god-like” knowledge and capabilities compared to the technological understanding from a century ago. This could lead to unprecedented advancements in AI's ability to learn from, predict and interact with both digital and physical environments in real time. The implications for the building industry include smarter, more adaptive systems with a potential thought-to-system interaction that could result in for example hyper-personalized indoor comfort, where a thought of a warmer room, results in the system adapting to your actual preference/ the collective preference.

11. Conclusion

Heimdal successfully met its objective of effectively managing and streamlining sensor data. It demonstrated a very robust performance in anomaly detection through algorithms like Local Outlier Factor and Random Forest, validating its effectiveness as a gatekeeper of information.

The journey through Heimdal's project highlighted the importance of precise anomaly detection within sensor data. A key lesson was the critical role of choosing the right algorithms where Local Outlier Factor and Random Forest stood out with an F1-score of 0.97.

Munin aimed to integrate and utilize cleaned sensor data and parsed conference data to predict coming sensor values based on number of conference attendees. While initial results showed moderate results, subsequent improvements in data pre-processing significantly enhanced model performance, especially for Random Forest achieving a high predictive accuracy of 0.904 or 90.4%. This high level of accuracy, combined with low MSE and MAE, demonstrates the model's reliability in predicting sensor values. This can be very insightful feedback-data for a live ventilation system, where it is being able to adapt to upcoming room climate needs, hence reducing the risk of bad indoor climate and guest complaints.

Munin's journey from initial moderate results to significant improvements in the second testing phase, demonstrated the importance of continual optimization in data processing and

model tuning. The project revealed that even with limited datasets, substantial gains in model performance are achievable with thorough data cleaning and appropriate model adjustments.

Hugin's objective was centered on an experimental approach to predict attendee numbers based on sensor data- a task more challenging than initially anticipated. Despite facing challenges with algorithm performance, Hugin offered profound insight into the complexities of data integration and prediction in dynamic environments.

Lessons learned from Hugin's journey include the importance of rigorous preprocessing, especially when dealing with challenging predictive tasks.

Understanding the challenge of data integration is essential in today's data-driven world. A clear observation from this project is that the model (Heimdall), which solely analysed sensor data, achieved near perfect performance. However, when numerical data are combined with other data types, the probability of achieving high model performance decreases significantly. This highlights a critical issue for the data industry: The difficulty of harmonizing disparate data sources. Addressing this challenge is essential for future advancements in data science. This is based on the fact that effective data harmonization from interdisciplinary sources will be key to unlocking the full potential of integrated data analysis.

The rapidly advancing ML and AI industry within building management and facilitation demands progressive harmonisation of data, increased processing power capacity and the integration of inter-disciplinary data in a unified/collective data domain. The findings in this report emphasize the importance of selecting and tailoring models based on the specific requirements and complexity of the data environment, guiding the development of more effective and responsive systems in Smart buildings.

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Appendix A:

1. Term definitions:

Internet of Things (IoT): The Internet of Things refers to the network of interconnected hardware devices, objects and components that communicate and exchange data with each other over the internet, enabling automation and smarter control of environments.

Industry 4.0: The fourth industrial revolution, characterized by the integration of digital technologies like IoT, AI and automation in manufacturing and production processes to enhance efficiency

Industry 5.0: The next industrial revolution, focusing on human-centric solutions where humans collaborate/merge with advanced technologies (especially AI and robots), emphasizing sustainability creativity, and personalization in industry.

Overfitting: A modelling error in machine learning where a model performs well on training data but poorly on new, unseen data because it has become too tailored to the specifics of the training set.

Ensemble learning methods: Machine learning techniques that combine predictions from multiple models to improve accuracy and robustness.

Principal Component Analysis (PCA): A statistical technique used to reduce the dimensionality of datasets, increasing interpretability while minimizing information loss. This is done by transforming the data into a set of linearly uncorrelated variables (principal components)

Energy Control: A Norwegian facilitation company providing energy management and smart building solutions, specializing in real-time data integration to optimize energy efficiency, indoor comfort and cost reduction in properties, through the use of sensors.

API (Application Programming Interface): A set of rules and protocols that allow different software applications to interact with another, sharing data and enabling the integration of different systems or use of third-party services.

Digital twins: Virtual models/components that replicate physical systems in real time, allowing simulation, monitoring and analysis of performance to optimize operations and predict outcomes.

Noisy data: Data that contains a high level of irrelevant or meaningless information, making it difficult to extract useful insights without cleaning or filtering the data.

Airthings: A Norwegian sensor company specializing in indoor air quality monitoring, offering products that measure factors like Co2 levels, humidity, temperature, airborne chemicals etc.

ACH (Air changes per hour): A metric used to measure how many times the air within a defined space is replaced with fresh air per hour. This is critical for monitoring and maintaining air quality in HVACR systems and rooms

HVACR: Heating, Ventilation, Air-Conditioning and Refrigerants

Hyperparameter tuning: The process of optimizing parameters that control the structure and behaviour of a machine learning model (f.ex learning rate, number of layers, tree depth) to improve its performance. These parameters are set before training and cannot be learned directly from the data

ANN (Artificial Neural Networks): Computational models inspired by the physical structure of the human brain. This consist of interconnected layers of nodes, used for tasks like pattern recognition, classification, and prediction in machine learning.